

A review of species diversity and distribution concerning environmental variables of Benthic Foraminifera around Marine Ecosystems Worldwide

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the distribution and diversity of benthic foraminifera across various coastal environments globally. Analyzing research from 2010 to 2023, we have explored the dominant foraminiferal assemblages in estuaries, foreshores, reefs and lagoons, coastal regions, shallow marine environments, mangrove ecosystems, offshore regions, oceans, and marginal seas. The most important findings of the literature search include the prevalence of calcareous foraminifera and stress-tolerant genera like *Ammonia* in estuaries. *Quinqueloculina* and *Elphidium* are dominant foreshore groups, while *Amphistegina* is a prominent reef and lagoon inhabitant. *Ammonia* and *Bolivina* are abundant across coastal regions. The study emphasizes the role of foraminifera as an environmental indicator. *Quinqueloculina* serves as a marker for pollution monitoring, while variations in foraminiferal abundance reflect changes in oxygen levels and sea level rise. The paper highlights the potential of benthic foraminifera for paleoecological studies and underscores the need for further research in underexplored coastal areas, alongside the development of efficient sampling and analysis techniques.

KEYWORDS: *Foraminifera; Marine ecosystems; Diversity; Abundance; Species richness*

1. INTRODUCTION

Approximately 15% of biodiversity are found in marine environment (Kim *et al.*, 2015). Coastal ecosystems, bridging land and sea, are vital for planetary health and hosting diverse habitats. Asia's coastlines host diverse marine life; Africa's range from mangroves to coral reefs supports biodiversity and fisheries; Europe's vast coastline offers varied habitats; North America faces conservation challenges across its coastal ecosystems; South America's coasts exhibit exceptional biodiversity, emphasizing the need for conservation efforts. Foraminifera, a single-celled creature primarily dwelling in sediment, exhibit diverse microhabitats, including epiphytic, epifaunal, and infaunal niches. They can be found in a wide range of environments, from transitional and coastal marine regions to the depths of the sea. These organisms have gained growing recognition as trustworthy ecological markers for evaluating and observing marine habitats, as well as for assessing ecological conditions (Romano *et al.*, 2021). Benthic foraminifera, with their abbreviated life spans and remarkable ability to endure in sedimentary archives, exhibit adaptability to their current habitats. This adaptability makes them reliable indicators for discerning both natural and human-induced environmental changes, spanning both the contemporary era and the geological past (Francescangeli *et al.*, 2021). The prevailing consensus is that the distribution of benthic foraminifera is influenced by a wide range of environmental parameters. These include water depth, substratum type, food availability, oxygen concentration, water currents, turbulence, light, salinity, pH, and temperature. Numerous studies highlight that the distribution of benthic foraminifera is shaped by the interplay of physical, chemical, and ecological variables (Fiorini, 2015).

This overview provides a summary of research investigating the biodiversity, ecology, and physiological reactions of benthic foraminifera. Diverse habitats including estuary, foreshore, reef and lagoons, coastal region, coastal lakes, shallow marine, mangrove ecosystem, offshore, ocean, and marginal sea, were examined for foraminifera diversity, and the dominant species were reported. Across continents, we review past studies, summarize what's happening now, find areas where more research is needed, and suggest what to study next. Additionally, we examine the challenges and advantages associated with employing benthic foraminifera as crucial determinants in previous studies conducted across continents, contributing to a subtle understanding of their relationships with the environment and highlighting directions for further exploration.

2. ESTIMATE OF BENTHIC FORAMINIFERA

Reviewing the extensive research on the global distribution of foraminifera from 2010 to 2023, 65 studies that focused on the diversity, species richness, and abundance status of the different ecosystems worldwide have been selected and discussed. It becomes evident that these microscopic marine organisms exhibit a diverse and widespread presence across oceans and seas. Various marine ecosystems host diverse microfauna contributing to the intricate web of marine life. The distribution and diversity of benthic foraminifera across varied marine ecosystems on different continents have been discussed and tabulated (Tables 1 to 10). Total number of Species recorded each year is represented in Figure 1.

Table 1: Abundance of foraminiferal species in Estuary

No. of species recorded	Dominant species	References
109	<i>C. poeyanum</i> , <i>Elphidium spp.</i> , <i>Quinqueloculina spp.</i> , <i>Triloculina spp.</i> , <i>Archaias angulatus</i> .	Sandra Schultz <i>et al.</i> , 2010
43	<i>Nonion depressulum</i> , <i>Quiqueloculina spp.</i> , <i>Simuloculina spp.</i> , <i>Triloculina spp.</i> , <i>Ammonia tepida</i> , <i>Ammonia nonion</i> .	Francisco Ruiz <i>et al.</i> , 2012
13	<i>Ammonia beccari</i> , <i>Mamilla C. refulgens</i> , <i>P. mediterraneensis</i> , <i>Siphonaperta spp.</i>	Phillips Olusegun A <i>et al.</i> , 2012
53	<i>M. fusca</i> , <i>A. aberdoveyensis</i> , <i>E. oceanensis</i> , <i>J. macrescens</i> , <i>T. inflata</i> ,	Camacho Sarita <i>et al.</i> , 2014

	<i>H. germanica</i> , <i>P. hyperhalina</i> , <i>B. ordinaria</i> .	
28	<i>Q. laevigata</i> , <i>N. calcar</i> .	Hannah M C Unsing and Maria L D G Lacuna, 2014
29	<i>Q. bicostata</i> , <i>C. splengeri</i> , <i>T. trigonula</i> , <i>Pararotalia sp.</i>	Shiela M Ganaway and Maria L D G Lacuna, 2014
39	<i>Hanzawaia nipponica</i> , <i>Elphidium advenum</i> , <i>Ammonia ketienziensis</i> , <i>Ammonia pauciloculata</i> , <i>Ammonia compressiuscula</i> , <i>Ammonia tepida</i> , <i>Haplophragmoides canariensis</i> , <i>Elphidium nakanokawaense</i> .	Tao Li <i>et al.</i> , 2014
38	<i>Ammonia beccarii</i> , <i>Ammonia tepida</i> , <i>Cibicides cushmani</i> , <i>Elphidium fichtellianum</i> .	Caroline P Onate and Maria L D G Lacuna, 2015
35	<i>Elphidiella hannai</i> , <i>Criboelphidium excavatum</i> , <i>Eggerella advena</i> ,	Elizabeth A Nesbitt <i>et al.</i> , 2015

	<i>Buccella frigida.</i>	
111	<i>L. lobatula,</i> <i>E. crispum,</i> <i>P. pertusus,</i> <i>R. bradyi,</i> <i>Quinqueloculina spp.,</i> <i>P. planatus,</i> <i>E. macellum.</i>	Andrea Benedetti and Virgilio Frezza, 2016
12	<i>Ammonia tepida,</i> <i>Haynesina germanica, Cribroelphidium</i> <i>excavatum.</i>	Mojtahid M <i>et al.</i> , 2016
116	<i>Cyclopyxis spp.,</i> <i>Centropyxis spp.,</i> <i>Diffflugia corona,</i> <i>Diffflugia urceolata.</i>	Lazaro Laut <i>et al.</i> , 2017
18	<i>Ammonia aomoriensis,</i> <i>A. beccarii,</i> <i>Quinqueloculina seminula.</i>	Shuaishuai Dong <i>et al.</i> , 2018
38	<i>Ammonia tepida,</i> <i>Cribroelphidium poeyanum,</i> <i>C. excavatum,</i> <i>Paratrochammina simplissima,</i> <i>Ammotium salsum,</i>	Christian Haller <i>et al.</i> , 2019

	<p><i>Ammobaculites exiguus, Miliammina fusca,</i></p> <p><i>Arenoparrella mexicana,</i></p> <p><i>Entzia macrescens,</i></p> <p><i>Trochamminita irregularis,</i></p> <p><i>Pseudothurammina limnetis.</i></p>	
42	<p><i>Ammobaculites exiguus,</i></p> <p><i>Ammotium salsum,</i></p> <p><i>Ammonia aoteana,</i></p> <p><i>Ammonia convexa,</i></p> <p><i>Trochammina sp. 1.</i></p>	Olugbenga T Fajemila <i>et al.</i> , 2020
76	<p><i>Rotalidium annectens,</i></p> <p><i>Ammonia aomoriensis,</i></p> <p><i>Buccella frigida,</i></p> <p><i>Textularia foliacea,</i></p> <p><i>Polskiammina asiatica, Protelphidium tuberculatum, Cribroelphidium magellanicum,</i></p> <p><i>Elphidium subincertum, Rotalinoides compressiuscula,</i></p> <p><i>Elphidium advenum,</i></p>	Yeda Guo <i>et al.</i> , 2020

	<p><i>Ammonia beccarii, Quinqueloculina lamarckiana, Haplophragmoides canariensis,</i></p> <p><i>Lagenammia atlantica, Ammoscalaria tenuimargo, Pararotalia nipponica,</i></p> <p><i>Ammonia tepida,</i></p> <p><i>Ammobaculites agglutinans,</i></p> <p><i>Criboelphidium magellanicum,</i></p> <p><i>Protelphidium tuberculatum.</i></p>	
9	<p><i>Ammonia aomoriensis,</i></p> <p><i>Haynesina germanica, Criboelphidium selseyense.</i></p>	Fabio Francescangeli <i>et al.</i> , 2021
93	<p><i>Pararotalia cananeaensis, Ammonia veneta,</i></p> <p><i>Anomalinulla sp.,</i></p> <p><i>O. carinata,</i></p> <p><i>Quinqueloculina moynensis.</i></p>	Nisan Sariaslan and Martin R Langer, 2021
16	<p><i>Elphidium,</i></p> <p><i>Hanzawaia,</i></p> <p><i>Pseudononion,</i></p> <p><i>Bulimina,</i></p> <p><i>Uvigerina.</i></p>	Stephen J Culver <i>et al.</i> , 2021

51	<i>Spiroplectinella antillarum</i> , <i>Agglutinella soriformis</i> , <i>Discorbis conicana</i> .	Amani Badawi <i>et al.</i> , 2022
32	<i>Elphidium macellum</i> , <i>Elphidium alvarezianum</i> , <i>Criboelphidium excavatum</i> , <i>Buccella</i> <i>peruviana</i> .	Emiliana Bernasconi <i>et</i> <i>al.</i> , 2022

Table 2: Abundance of foraminiferal species in Foreshore

No. of species recorded	Dominant species	References
111	<i>Neorotalia calcar</i> , <i>Amphistegina spp.</i> , <i>Quinqueloculina lamarckiana</i> , <i>Pararotalia calcariformata</i> , <i>Rotorbis auberii</i> , <i>Elphidium striatopunctatum</i> , <i>Eponides</i> <i>repandus</i> , <i>Quinqueloculina cf. Q. lamarckiana</i> , <i>Q. vulgaris</i> , <i>Ammonia convexa</i> ,	Anna E Weinmann and Martin R Langer, 2017

	<p><i>Elphidium limbatum</i> sp. 2, <i>Glabratellina</i> sp. 1,</p> <p><i>Rosalina bradyi</i>,</p> <p><i>Peneroplis pertusus</i>,</p> <p><i>Sorites orbiculus</i>.</p>	
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Table 3: Abundance of foraminiferal species in Reef and Lagoons

No. of species recorded	Dominant species	References
40	<p><i>A. tepida</i>,</p> <p><i>A. parkinsoniana</i>,</p> <p><i>E. excavatum</i>.</p>	Claudia Gutterres Vilela <i>et al.</i> , 2011
270	<p><i>Amphistegina</i> sp. 1,</p> <p><i>Operculina ammonoides</i>, <i>Amphistegina radiata</i>,</p> <p><i>Nummulites venosa</i>,</p> <p><i>Neoeponides bradyi</i>,</p> <p><i>Textularia</i> cf. <i>T. cushmani</i>, <i>Textularia</i> gr. <i>foliacea</i>, <i>Spiroloculina</i>, <i>nummiformis</i>,</p> <p><i>Textularia</i> sp. 5.</p>	Justin H Parker and Eberhard Gischler, 2011
12	<p><i>Ammonia</i> spp.,</p>	William J Foster <i>et al.</i> , 2012

	<i>Quinqueloculina bicostata</i> , <i>Quinqueloculina seminula</i> , <i>Quinqueloculina bicostata</i> .	
169	<i>Amphistegina spp.</i> , <i>Neorotalia calcar</i> , <i>Ammonia convexa</i> .	Jens M Thissen and Martin R Langer, 2013
158	<i>Textularia hauerii</i> , <i>Quinqueloculina cf. Q. lamarckiana</i> , <i>Elphidium cf. E. limbatum</i> , <i>P. acervalis</i> , <i>T. trigonula</i> , <i>Pseudotriloculina cf. P. oblonga</i> .	Martin R Langer <i>et al.</i> , 2013
287	<i>Quinqueloculina</i> , <i>Triloculina</i> , <i>Spiroloculina</i> .	Chienhsun Chen and Hui- Ling Lin, 2017
35	<i>Ammonia beccarii</i> , <i>Quinqueloculina</i> <i>rhodiensis</i> , <i>Q. seminulum</i> , <i>Ammobaculites agglutinans</i> .	Michael Martinez-Colon <i>et</i> <i>al.</i> , 2017
17	<i>Ammonia tepida</i> , <i>Ammonia parkinsoniana</i> , <i>Criboelphidium excavatum</i> .	Pierre Belart <i>et al.</i> , 2018

8900	<i>Quinqueloculina</i> , <i>Amphistegina</i> .	Marcela Costa Pompeu <i>et al.</i> , 2019
2	<i>Amphistegina gibbosa</i> , <i>Amphisorus hemprichii</i> .	Patricia P B Eichler <i>et al.</i> , 2019

Table 4: Abundance of foraminiferal species in Coastal region

No. of species recorded	Dominant species	References
175	<i>Globocassidulina subglobosa</i> , <i>Uvigerina peregrina</i> , <i>Bulimina marginata</i> , <i>Buccella peruviana</i> , <i>Bolivina striatula</i> , <i>Textularia earlandi</i> , <i>Arenoparella mexicana</i> , <i>Globigerinoides rubber</i> , <i>Globorotalia menardii</i> .	Eichler PPB <i>et al.</i> , 2012
256	<i>Ammonia convexa</i> , <i>Amphistegina lobifera</i> , <i>Amphistegina radiata</i> , <i>Challengerella bradyi</i> , <i>Neorotalia calcar</i> .	Johannes Pignatti <i>et al.</i> , 2012
3	<i>Haynesina germanica</i> , <i>Ammonia sp.</i> ,	Salha A Saad and Christopher M Wade, 2016

	<i>Elphidium williamsoni.</i>	
221	<p><i>Nonion sp. 1,</i></p> <p><i>Quinqueloculina sp. 1, Asterorotalia dentata,</i></p> <p><i>Bolivina cf. B. persiensis,</i></p> <p><i>Asterorotalia sp. 3,</i></p> <p><i>Rotalinoides gaimardi,</i></p> <p><i>Ammonia sp. 1,</i></p> <p><i>Quinqueloculina sp.,</i></p> <p><i>Bolivina cf. B. striatula,</i></p> <p><i>Nonion sp. 2.</i></p>	Abduljamiu O Amao <i>et al.</i> , 2018
55	<p><i>A. beccarii,</i></p> <p><i>S. aspera,</i></p> <p><i>H. depressula,</i></p> <p><i>Triloculina schreiberiana.</i></p>	Luisa Bergamin <i>et al.</i> , 2019
451	<p><i>Quinqueloculina,</i></p> <p><i>Triloculina,</i></p> <p><i>Spiroloculina,</i></p> <p><i>Elphidium,</i></p> <p><i>Ammonia.</i></p>	Eqbal Al-Enezi <i>et al.</i> , 2020
66	<p><i>Ammobaculites exiguus,</i></p> <p><i>Ammonia tepida,</i></p>	Fatin Izzati Minhat <i>et al.</i> , 2020

	<p><i>Asterorotalia cf. A. pulchella,</i> <i>Haplophragmoides cf. H.</i> <i>canariensis,</i> <i>Nonion subturgidum,</i> <i>Pararotalia ozawai, Quinqueloculina</i> <i>seminulum, Textularia aff. T.</i> <i>earlandi.</i></p>	
31	<p><i>Peneroplis planatus,</i> <i>Sorites orbiculus,</i> <i>Coscinospira hemprichii,</i> <i>Ammonia tepida,</i> <i>C. hemprichii,</i> <i>P. planatus.</i></p>	<p>Khaled Al-Kahtany <i>et al.</i>, 2020</p>
10318	<p><i>Textularia conica,</i> <i>Pararotalia sp.,</i> <i>Cibicides lobatulus,</i> <i>Planorbulina mediterraneensis,</i> <i>Bolivina cf. pseudopunctata,</i> <i>Cassidulina laevigata,</i> <i>Ammonia beccarii,</i> <i>Bolivina tortuosa,</i> <i>Bulimina elongata,</i> <i>Cassidulina obtusa,</i></p>	<p>Susanne Hempel and Burg Flemming, 2021</p>

	<p><i>Elphidium advenum</i>,</p> <p><i>Cassidulina laevigata</i>,</p> <p><i>Bolivina cf. pseudopunctata</i>,</p> <p><i>Bulimina elongata</i>,</p> <p><i>Ammonia beccarii</i>,</p> <p><i>Elphidium advenum</i>,</p> <p><i>Bolivina tortuosa</i>.</p>	
5	<p><i>Ammonia beccarii</i>,</p> <p><i>Pararotalia calcariformata</i>,</p> <p><i>Elphidium advenum</i>,</p> <p><i>Eponides repandus</i>,</p> <p><i>Quinqueloculina bosciiana</i>.</p>	Trivedi M H <i>et al.</i> , 2021
15	<p><i>T. inflata</i>,</p> <p><i>J. macrescens</i>,</p> <p><i>T. comprimata</i>,</p> <p><i>B. pseudomacrescens</i>,</p> <p><i>Haplophragmoides spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>A. inepta</i>.</p>	Jennifer S Walker <i>et al.</i> , 2023

Table 5: Abundance of foraminiferal species in Coastal lakes

No. of species recorded	Dominant species	References
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5	<i>Ammonia tepida.</i>	Sherif M El Baz, 2014
15	<i>Buccella frigida,</i> <i>Elphidium albiumbilicatum.</i>	Yeon Gyu Lee <i>et al.</i> , 2015

Table 6: Abundance of foraminiferal species in Shallow marine

No. of species recorded	Dominant species	References
93	<i>Ammonia beccarii,</i> <i>Spiroloculina excavata,</i> <i>S. depressa,</i> <i>Quinqueloculina dimidiata,</i> <i>Q. seminula,</i> <i>Q. costata,</i> <i>Triloculina sp.,</i> <i>Bolivina spp.</i>	Seyyed Mohammad Bagher <i>et al.</i> , 2014
29	<i>Amphistegina papillosa,</i> <i>Assilina ammonoides,</i> <i>Assilina ammonoides,</i> <i>Heterolepa dutemplei, Discorbinella bertheloti,</i> <i>Textularia agglutinans, Cylindroclavulina bradyi.</i>	Nazihah Azmi <i>et al.</i> , 2020
5	<i>Cassidulina laevigata,</i>	

	<p><i>Cassidulina carinata,</i> <i>Eponides umbonatus,</i> <i>Bolivina seminuda,</i> <i>Hopkinsinella glabra, Eubuliminella exilis,</i> <i>Rotaliatinopsis semiinvoluta, Hopkinsinella</i> <i>glabra, Epistominella exigua,</i> <i>Bulimina arabiensis,</i> <i>Bulimina elegans,</i> <i>Bolivina earlandi,</i> <i>Bulimina aculeata,</i> <i>Globocassidulina subglobosa.</i></p>	<p>Amrata Kaithwar <i>et al.</i>, 2020</p>
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Table 7: Abundance of foraminiferal species in Mangrove ecosystem

No. of species recorded	Dominant species	References
59	<i>Rotalidium accectans.</i>	Vidhya P and Rajashekar K Patil, 2014
15	<i>Quinqueloculina sp.,</i> <i>Jadammina macrescens.</i>	Areen Sen <i>et al.</i> , 2015
16	<i>A. beccarii,</i> <i>T. inflata,</i> <i>H. bradyi.</i>	Jeyabal G <i>et al.</i> 2016

Table 8: Abundance of foraminiferal species in Offshore

No. of species recorded	Dominant species	References
29	<i>Ammonia beccarii</i> , <i>A. dentate</i> , <i>Spiroloculina communis</i> , <i>Quinquiloculina seminulam</i> , <i>Pararotalina nipponica</i> .	Babu K <i>et al.</i> , 2014
66	<i>Asterorotalia pulchella</i> , <i>Ammobaculites exiguus</i> , <i>Ammonia</i> , <i>Elphidium</i> .	Faiz N N, 2017
160	<i>Stainforthia compressa</i> , <i>Elphidium discoidale</i> , <i>Ammonia tepida</i> , <i>Bolivina lowmani</i> , <i>Ammonia pauciloculata</i> , <i>Buliminella tenuata</i> , <i>Triloculina trigonula</i> , <i>Bolivina striatula spinata</i> , <i>Nonionella atlantica</i> , <i>Quinqueloculina compta</i> , <i>Quinqueloculina bosciana</i> , <i>Bolivina ordinaria</i> ,	Machain-Castillo <i>et al.</i> , 2019

	<i>Bigenerina irregularis,</i> <i>Uvigerina peregrina.</i>	
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Table 9: Abundance of foraminiferal species in Ocean

No. of species recorded	Dominant species	References
36	<i>Gyroidina sp,</i> <i>Pyrgo murrhina,</i> <i>Bulimina alazanensis,</i> <i>Pullenia subcarinata, Discopulvinulina</i> <i>bertheloti, Epistominella exigua,</i> <i>Pullenie bulloides,</i> <i>Epistominella exigua,</i> <i>Pullenia bulloides,</i> <i>Gyroidina neosoldani,</i> <i>Astrononion umbilicatalum, Planulina</i> <i>wullerstorfi,</i> <i>Oolina apiculata,</i> <i>Oolina desophora,</i> <i>Laticarinina pauperata,</i> <i>Fissurina alveolata, Nummoloculina sp,</i> <i>Pullenia quinqueloba,</i>	Nadimikeri Jayaraju <i>et al.</i> , 2010

	<p><i>Lagena stelligera,</i> <i>Oridorsalis umbonatus,</i> <i>Melonis sphaeroides,</i> <i>Chilostomella ovoidea,</i> <i>Uvigerina hispido-costata, Eggerella</i> <i>bradyi,</i> <i>Karreriella bradyi.</i></p>	
44	<p><i>Buccella peruviana,</i> <i>Elphidium aff. Poeyanum,</i> <i>Bulimina cf. pseudoaffinis, Cibicides</i> <i>dispars,</i> <i>C. aknerianus,</i> <i>Quinqueloculina patagonica.</i></p>	Emiliana Bernasconi <i>et al.</i> , 2018

Table 10: Abundance of foraminiferal species in Marginal Sea

No. of species recorded	Dominant species	References
6	<p><i>Ammonia beccarii caspica, Elphidium</i> <i>littorale caspicus, Milliammina fusca,</i> <i>Ammotium sp.</i></p>	Mina Sadough <i>et al.</i> , 2013
6	<p><i>Nonionella basispinata, Epistominella</i> <i>bradyana,</i></p>	Pettit L R <i>et al.</i> , 2013

	<p><i>Bulimina marginata</i>,</p> <p><i>E. bradyana</i>,</p> <p><i>B. marginata</i>,</p> <p><i>Eponides sp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Elphidium excavatum (Terquem)</i>,</p> <p><i>N. basispinata</i>.</p>	
205	<p><i>Amphistegina spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Cibicides spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Planorbulina mediterranensis, Elphidium spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Criboelphidium spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Eponides coryelli</i>,</p> <p><i>Hanzawaya spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Rosalina spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Reussella spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Pseudononion spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Nonionella spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Amphistegina lessonii</i>,</p> <p><i>Bulimina aculeata</i>,</p> <p><i>Bulimina alzanensis</i>,</p> <p><i>Bulimina marginata</i>,</p> <p><i>Globocassidulina subglobosa</i>,</p>	Flavia Fiorini, 2015

	<p><i>Planulina wuellerstorfi</i>, <i>Uvigerina proboscidea</i>,</p> <p><i>Adelosina polygona</i>,</p> <p><i>Adelosina lamarkiana</i>.</p>	
304	<p><i>A. beccarii</i>,</p> <p><i>P. nipponica</i>,</p> <p><i>Hoeglundina elegans</i>,</p> <p><i>E. advenum</i>,</p> <p><i>Ammonia cf. indopacifica</i>,</p> <p><i>P. cribrorepandus</i>,</p> <p><i>Textularia sp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Quinqueloculina costata</i>,</p> <p><i>Quinqueloculina contorta</i>,</p> <p><i>Cassidulina norvangi</i>, <i>Cassidulina sp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Paracassidulina minuta</i>, <i>Paracassidulina cf. neocarinata</i>, <i>Globocassidulina venustas</i>,</p> <p><i>Globocassidulina spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Elphidium etigoense</i>,</p> <p><i>Elphidium subincertum</i>,</p> <p><i>Nonion nicobarense</i>, <i>Quinqueloculina akneriana</i>, <i>Haplophragmoides sp.</i>,</p>	Sangjin Kim <i>et al.</i> , 2015

	<p><i>Trochammina pacifica, Ammobaculites</i> <i>sp.</i>,</p> <p><i>A. beccarii</i>,</p> <p><i>E. subincertum</i>,</p> <p><i>Buccella sp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Eggerella advena</i>,</p> <p><i>Textularia cuneata</i>,</p> <p><i>T. pacifica</i>.</p>	
124	<p><i>Ammoglobigerina, globigeriniformis</i>,</p> <p><i>Ammonia tepida</i>,</p> <p><i>Cibicidoides lobatulus, Eggerelloides</i> <i>advenus, Lepidodeuterammina ochracea</i>,</p> <p><i>Patellina corrugata</i>,</p> <p><i>Reophax dentaliniformis, Rosalina</i> <i>bradyi</i>.</p>	Elena Romano <i>et al.</i> , 2021
236	<p><i>Lagenammina difflugiformis</i>,</p> <p><i>Globobulimina spp.</i>,</p> <p><i>Uvigerina peregrina</i>,</p> <p><i>Bolivina plicata</i>.</p>	Patarroyo G D and Martinez, 2021
	<p><i>Ammonia tepida</i>,</p> <p><i>Bulimina elongata</i>,</p> <p><i>Bulimina marginata</i>,</p>	Margarita D Dimiza <i>et al.</i> , 2022

	<i>Nonionella turgida.</i>	
50	<i>Epistominella exigua, Oridorsalis umbonatus.</i>	Michael Hesemann, 2023

Fig. 1: Total number of Species recorded each year.

CONCLUSION

Numerous researchers have conducted extensive research on the diversity and distribution of foraminiferal taxa in coastal areas across the globe. The findings indicate that calcareous forms predominantly dominated the foraminiferal assemblages. In the estuary, stress-tolerant genera, such as *Ammonia*, dominate foraminiferal assemblages. *Quinqueloculina*, *Haynesina*, *Elphidium*, *Criboelphidium*, *Triloculina* are the most abundant genera found. Foreshore regions are dominated by the genera *Quinqueloculina* and *Elphidium*. *Amphistegina*, *Quinqueloculina*, *Textularia*, *Spiroloculina*. *Amphistegina* was considered to be the leading producer of calcium carbonate and

is called an ecosystem engineer. *Ammonia*, *Amphistegina* are the most dominant genera found in reef and lagoon regions. The mentioned taxa play a significant role in the formation of reef carbonates, influencing the diversity and species richness of associated assemblages through their abundance and widespread presence. *Ammonia*, *Bolivina*, *Elphidium*, *Quinqueloculina*, *Textularia*, *Triloculina*, *Haynesina*, are the abundant genera found in the coastal regions. *Quinqueloculina* genus is a strong biological indicator for ongoing in situ monitoring of anthropogenic pollution in coastal marine ecosystems with benthic foraminifera. Shallow marine is dominated by the genera *Cassidulina*, *Bulimina*, *Assilina*, *Bolivina*, *Quinqueloculina*. *Ammonia*, *Quinqueloculina* are the genera dominated in mangrove ecosystems. They are mainly dominated by agglutinated species. *Ammonia*, *Quinqueloculina*, *Bolivina* genera dominate the offshore regions. *Bulimina*, *Cibicides* genera are abundant in Ocean. *Ammonia*, *Bolivina*, *Bulimina*, *Nonionella*, and *Rosalina* are the most abundant genera found in marginal sea regions. A high diversity of foraminiferal species indicates that many shallow-water bottom-dwelling organisms seem to possess the ability to withstand exposure to temperature extremes that occur during the day. Polluted sites exhibited unique assemblages and taxa with increased tolerance to various stressors. These serve as valuable bioindicators for future studies on environmental disruptions. Benthic foraminifera serve as effective indicators for detecting early signs of potential anthropogenic pollution in the marine environment. Benthic foraminifera in intertidal zones are commonly employed as markers for assessing changes in relative sea levels. Variations in the abundance of benthic foraminifera can serve as an indicator of oxygen depletion. Benthic assemblages have the potential to retain the initial community structure and essential environmental information, making them valuable indicators for palaeoecological studies. Despite challenges such as variability in species distribution and environmental factors, the advantages include their sensitivity to environmental changes and their

potential as reliable indicators. There is a necessity to promote foraminiferal research in underexplored coastal areas and to create efficient, cost-effective techniques for sampling, processing, counting, and cataloging foraminiferal taxa. This is crucial for future research in less-studied regions worldwide.

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